

DESIGN OF A ROLL-CONTROL SUSPENSION LINK USING COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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SUMMARY: The aim of this study was to reduce the weight of the current all-steel forged suspension link fitted on French Railways TGV (High Speed Train) bogies by incorporating composite materials. Weight saving of the order of 30% was specified.

A previous analysis of the part function and its working environment had been performed in order to decide whether a partial or a total substitution of composites for steel was appropriate.

The first part of the study assessed engineering feasibility by a global approach to materials systems and selection. The result showed that the most cost-effective and technologically viable solution was to retain the existing forged steel rod-ends and replace the shank by a bonded composite material tube.

Prototypes consisting of steel-on-steel, glass/epoxy on steel and carbon/epoxy on steel combinations were made and tested. The steel on steel specimen was used as a benchmark for the others. Results on glass/epoxy tubes showed good correlation during static testing. However, their relatively low resistance to cyclic loads led to the replacement of the glass/epoxy material by carbon/epoxy tubes.

A total of three carbon/epoxy on steel suspension links were used in the test programme. The 30% weight saving was confirmed. These specimens met the design requirements and performed well when compared to the theoretically predicted values both in static and fatigue testing modes. It is intended to put two prototypes into service on a bogie.

KEYWORDS: application of composite materials, testing, static and fatigue behaviour

INTRODUCTION

This study was commissioned by the ACR works of GEC-Alstom with the aim of using composite materials technology to make weight savings in certain applications. The part chosen for the study was a suspension link forming part of the anti-roll system of a high speed train (TGV) bogie. Being a feasibility study only the mechanical behaviour aspects were to be examined; no account was taken of the long-term effects on composite material performance.

Expected weight saving was set at least at 30%. There are four links per bogie of average weight 10kg which in fact represents a relatively insignificant gain however it was felt that a successful link design could be fitted to a bogie without any safety implications.

The study was broadly divided into four main sections covering the following topics:

- a) Analysis of the existing suspension link and its working environment. Exploration of various ways of introducing composite materials into the construction.
- b) Finite element analysis to optimize the choice of composite materials and bond-line geometry.
- c) Fabrication of full size test samples and validation through mechanical testing.
- d) Optimization of the chosen solution to meet the specified requirement.

After the completion of the test programme three composite suspension links were manufactured in conformity with the specification, two of which were fitted to a bogie for testing under real conditions.

FUNCTIONALITY OF THE EXISTING LINK

The current part is made from a forging of AF42 steel (yield stress 42 MPa) and weighs 10 kg. It is fitted to the bogie and the anti-roll bar through silentbloc bushings pressed into the end eyes and held by circlips. Service loads are tension and compression only, static rating being ± 50 kN and the dynamic rating ± 30 kN in fatigue. Life expectancy is 30 years although the actual number of cycles this represents is difficult to verify. Simple dimensional analysis showed that in the shank the safety factor is 6 in monotonic loading and 3 in fatigue which obviously represents considerable overdesign.

The first part of the study was a research exercise on a solution that would possibly give the most weight saving. A link made up of light alloy end fittings incorporated into a filament-wound composite structure has been studied. The reduction in weight was estimated to be about 6 kg which is appreciable. However the approach was not justified from time scale and cost considerations as well as the potential development difficulties.

A second and more pragmatic approach was being simultaneously conducted which consisted of replacing the central solid steel part of the suspension link by a light-weight composite tube as showed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Suspension link with shank made from UD composite tube

As the service loads in this section are limited to tension and compression only since the bushings remove any applied moment at the ends, then a tube made from unidirectional composite material was thought to be a good choice.

It was intended that assembly between the composite material and the steel end-fittings should be by adhesive bonding. Initial estimations showed that the 30% weight-saving was theoretically possible, thus meeting the specification, provided the tube was of maximum length compatible with a sound adhesive bond.

Literature shows [1] that composite materials fatigue behaviour is generally good so it was felt the performance of the new link would depend largely on the efficiency of the adhesive bond.

DESIGN OF THE BONDED JOINT

In view of the importance of a correctly designed bond [2-6] the dimensioning of the end fittings was performed using finite element analysis. The calculations were done using ACCORD-2D which is a two dimensional elastic model. To ensure a favourable stress distribution it was decided to vary bond line thickness and to allow for geometry changes at the highly stressed end of the joint.

Basic materials properties used in the calculation are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Basic materials properties used in the finite element calculation

Material	Young's modulus E (GPa)	Poisson's ratio •
Steel	210.0	0.30
Epoxy resin for the bond	1.4	0.33
unidirectional glass-epoxy tube	40.0	0.35

The results of the calculations enabled the joint configuration to be defined as showed in Figure 2. Bondline thickness was fixed at a nominal 0.4 mm.

Figure 2. Bond geometry defined by finite element calculation

By assuming that the failure criterion should be maximum shear stress in the bond and applying it to the numerical data it is possible to predict overall joint performance. Taking the shear elastic limit of the epoxy adhesive; $\tau(\text{yield}) = 20 \text{ MPa}$; $\tau(\text{failure}) = 37 \text{ MPa}$, which give a notion of the safety factors. However this is not the case in fatigue; a reasonable assumption is that the fatigue strength is limited to between 10 and 20% of the static strength.

In the event that bond strength should need to be optimized after initial testing, then this could be done by increasing bonding contact area or by the choice of a more rigid composite material such as unidirectional carbon/epoxy.

TEST SAMPLE PREPARATION

Materials and Joint Dimensions Configuration

Each sample consisted of a composite tube middle section and two steel end-fittings to enable the adaptation to the test machine to be made either by pinning or by bolting. The fittings were machined from XC 48 steel which has very similar characteristics to the original forged suspension link. Bonding was carried out at 120°C.

The finite element analysis had showed that the composite tube should be of a material having an elastic modulus at least as high as unidirectional glass/epoxy ($V_f=60\%$). At the time of making the samples no unidirectional glass/epoxy composite tube in the required dimensions was available, hence the initial samples were made using tubing reinforced by glass woven roving having a warp/weft ratio of 60/40. Materials properties of the samples are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Materials properties of the test samples

Material	E(GPa)	ν	τ -yield(MPa)	τ -failure(MPa)
Steel XC 48	210.0	0.33	400	700
Epoxy PERMABOND ESP 110	1.4	0.33	20	37
			X ⁺ (MPa)	X ⁻ (MPa)
Woven glass/epoxy tube (warp)	30.0	0.35	690	375
UD carbon/epoxy tube	230.0	0.35	3530	

The first samples were made to the dimensions given by the numerical calculation and the joint length was set at 30 mm (Fig. 2). In the first static tests premature cracking at the joint free edge was observed and the design load was not attained. This was thought to be due to the nature of the glass fibre composite used so it was decided to increase the bond length to 38 mm. This allowed the design load to be attained so all subsequent samples had the same joint length.

In order to attain the fatigue load, one test sample was made with steel XC 48 tubes and three made with unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite tubes.

Bonding and joint preparation

All bonded surfaces were prepared using 200 then 400 grade emery paper to produce a smooth mat surface. Degreasing was done by trichlorethylene dip and warm air drying.

The thickness of the internal diameter bond layer at 0.4 mm was maintained by a machined recess in the tube fitting onto a shoulder on the end piece. The outside diameter bond thickness was obtained by using four slips of thin rubber to centre the two half shells. The

slips did not run the full joint length to avoid creating any stress concentration and no significant loss of bond area was incurred by this technique.

Bonding time was a full two hours at 120°C followed by oven cooling.

TESTING

As this was a feasibility study and the main area of interest was in the performance of the bonded joint, no particular precaution was taken to monitor the behaviour of the composite tube. Apart from some static testing to provide reference values all the testing was in the dynamic mode.

The fatigue tests were carried out at the ACR plant by GEC-Alsthom on a Schenck 160 kN dynamic testing system.

Static loading

As the study progressed it was found necessary to make different types of specimen in order to reach the specified performance. However all specimens were geometrically identical and thus underwent the same testing schedule.

Static testing in tension and compression was done using loading speeds of 80 or 160 N/s. All the static test results obtained on various samples are presented in Table 3.

As a general rule local cracking of the samples in tension was seen at the free stressed end of the bond well in advance of any non-linear behaviour on the load/elongation curve. By increasing the bond length from 30 mm to 38 mm the initiation of the local cracking occurred at a much higher load level which lead to corresponding increases in joint yield and breaking strengths. Under compression loading, any global non-linear behaviour occurring was observed before the failure of the composite tube. One of the samples (N.5) was tested in compression up to 100 kN and then in tension to the failure; no significant effect of compression on tensile strength was observed.

Table 3. The static test results obtained on the samples with glass/epoxy composite tube

L1=50 mm, L2=30 mm, P(kN)					
N0	Load	P-crack	P-yield	P-break	Failure mode
1	tension	58	75	139	bond
2	tension	55	98	140	bond
3	tension	50	102	132	bond
4	compression			156	composite tube
5	compression then tension	50	86	137	bond joint
Tension: Pc=53±5 kN, Py=90±6 kN, Pb=137±3 kN.					
Compression: Pf=156 kN					
L1=50 mm, L2=38 mm, P (kN)					
6	tension	66	92	152	bond
7	tension	85	100	140	bond
8	tension	65	90	144	bond
9	compression			120	composite tube
Tension: Pc=72±13 kN, Py=94±6 kN, Pb=145±7 kN.					
Compression: Pf=120 kN					

One of the samples with carbon fibre tube was tested in tension only. Crack initiation at the free stressed edge was around 110 kN after which the load/elongation curve behaved non-linearly. This value is some 50% higher than previous values obtained with glass fibre

samples and confirms the well-known fact that sound bonds are made between members of similar stiffnesses. The breaking load of this sample was 158 kN.

Tensile failure occurs in the bond length while compression failure occurs in the composite tube. Examination of a failed bond shows fragments of composite tube adhering to the steel substrate and traces of epoxy resin on the tube indicating that the failure line oscillated between both substrates. This evidence confirms the choice of adhesive and the assembly technology.

Overall static behaviour was good and the results were well with the specification.

Fatigue testing

Fatigue testing was carried out under severe conditions going from 30 kN in tension to 30 kN in compression following a sinusoidal variation. Throughout the test sample stiffness was measured as a function of the number of cycles. The signal was processed by a personal computer set-up.

Fatigue life of glass/epoxy samples

For glass/epoxy samples, the test programme was started by fatiguing directly two specimens to failure with no prior mechanical loading being imposed. As is showed in Table 4 the fatigue life was fairly low and the usual cracking at the free stressed end of the joint was observed. As a result it was decided to pre-load the sample to 70 kN before starting the fatigue cycling. This load value represents the onset of local cracking. As can be seen in Table 4 this treatment seems beneficial although more testing would be necessary to confirm the trend.

Table 4. The fatigue test results obtained on the samples with glass/epoxy composite tube

NO.	Loading (f=12Hz)	Fatigue life (number of cycles)	failure mode
1	fatigue ± 30 kN	$209 \cdot 10^3$	bond joint
2	fatigue ± 30 kN	$232 \cdot 10^3$	bond joint
3	static tension 70kN fatigue ± 30 kN	$506 \cdot 10^3$	bond joint

A number of conclusions were drawn from these preliminary tests which lead to some modification in the programme.

- The results showed that fatigue life was well below that expected.
- Pre-stressing might be a useful means of increasing fatigue life.
- Bonds fail showing adhesive-cohesive behaviour.
- Sample stiffness remained fairly constant until the few minutes preceding bond failure.
- Concomitant with bond failure the local temperature in the bond zone increased by about 10°C.
- The stress concentration at the free joint end seems responsible for the low fatigue life.

Fatigue life of steel sample

This sample was prepared using a tube and end fittings made from the same steel in order to investigate the role of part stiffness on bond fatigue strength. Apart from the material used the sample was identical to its composite counterparts.

The fatigue testing was begun with no prior static loading of the part. Test conditions were ± 30 kN at 5 Hz.

The now classic local cracking was observed at about $400 \cdot 10^3$ cycles with no apparent change in overall stiffness. With still no evolution in stiffness the frequency was increased to 12 Hz from $1.3 \cdot 10^6$ cycles onwards. The test was stopped at $6 \cdot 10^6$ cycles with no apparent change in overall stiffness.

This one-off test was seen to indicate that a high modulus composite solution would be viable.

Fatigue life of carbon/epoxy sample

In the same way as the steel sample a unidirectional carbon/epoxy part (their characteristics are presented in Table 2) was prepared using exactly the same bonding configuration. The test results obtained are presented in Table 5. The loading spectrum is somewhat varied as rapid confirmation of the usefulness of the solution was required. As the test continued without apparent loss of sample stiffness the frequency was progressively increased to gain time. Probably the load conditions of ± 30 kN were too low but it was felt inappropriate to modify the specification at this stage.

During the test crack initiation occurred at about $300 \cdot 10^3$ cycles, slightly lower than the steel version. An attempt to measure the extent of crack propagation was made using infra-red thermography. The test frequency was deliberately increased in order to initiate local heating that could be detected. In spite of an increase to 20 Hz during about $60 \cdot 10^3$ cycles nothing was found. Any temperature increase was uniform and corresponded with an increase in the hydraulic actuator temperature. It was concluded that any crack propagation must be slight and have no significant effect on fatigue life in this case. Thereafter the load was increased until bond failure at $11.1 \cdot 10^6$ cycles.

Table 5. Fatigue test results obtained on the samples with carbon/epoxy composite tubes

Frequency	Load	Cycles	Observations
5 Hz	± 30 kN	$296 \cdot 10^3$	local cracking at the free joint end crack propagation detection using infra-red thermography
20 Hz	± 30 kN	$357 \cdot 10^3$	
10 Hz	± 30 kN	$450 \cdot 10^3$	failure in bond
20 Hz	± 30 kN	$1.5 \cdot 10^6$	
20 Hz	± 40 kN	$10.0 \cdot 10^6$	
20 Hz	± 50 kN	$10.5 \cdot 10^6$	
20 Hz	± 60 kN	$11.0 \cdot 10^6$	
20 Hz	± 60 kN	$11.1 \cdot 10^6$	

Based on this performance it was decided to proceed with the fabrication of three prototype suspension links, two of which were to be fitted to commercially operated trains for field trials.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has showed the feasibility of making steel to composites bonds that can have significant mechanical strength and fatigue life.

The best compromise was found to be a unidirectional carbon/epoxy tube due to its high modulus.

Inspite of high performance some local cracking at the free stressed end of an adhesive bond is inevitable though not necessarily important.

The combination of carbon/epoxy and steel enabled a weight saving of 30% to be made as required by the specification.

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